

AN INNOVATIVE MECHANICAL TESTING METHOD FOR MEASURING YOUNG'S MODULUS OF MULTI-LAYERED MATERIALS (OWN-WEIGHT CANTILEVER METHOD)

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ABSTRACT

This report deals with an innovative testing method (*Own-Weight Cantilever Method*) to measure Young's modulus of each layer in a thin flexible multi-layered materials (thin plate, rod, wire). A newly developed method is based on the large deformation theory considering large deformation behaviors due to own-weight in thin flexible multi-layered materials. Analytical solutions are derived by using Bessel Functions. By just measuring the horizontal displacement or the vertical displacement at a free end of a cantilever, Young's modulus of each layer can be easily obtained for various thin and long flexible multi-layered materials. Measurements were carried out on a two-layered material (plate) consisting of SUS (a stainless steel material) and PVC (a high-polymer material). The results confirm that the new method is suitable for thin flexible multi-layered plates. In the meantime, the new method proposed in this paper can be applied widely to measure Young's modulus of every thin layers formed by PVD, CVD, Electrodeposition, Coating, Paint, Cladding, Lamination, and others.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, flexible multi-layered materials with very high performance are widely used to establish cost-effective processing with regard to long-term performance. Therefore, large deformation analyses of these flexible multi-layered materials have attracted attention considerably in the design of mechanical springs, fabrics and various thin-walled structures (aerospace structures, ship, car, etc.). An investigation of large deformation behaviors occurring in flexible materials is necessary for evaluation of mechanical properties such as Young's modulus. Here, this paper describes a new Young's modulus measuring method (*Own-Weight Cantilever Method*). Applying a nonlinear large deformation theory, Analytical solutions are derived by using Bessel Functions. By using this method, Young's modulus of each layer in a thin and long flexible multi-layered material can be easily obtained by just measuring the horizontal displacement or the vertical displacement at the free end of the cantilever.

In order to assess the applicability of the proposed method, several experiments were carried out using a two-layered material (SUS: a stainless steel material + PVC: a high-polymer material). As a result, the new method was found to be suitable for flexible multi-layered materials. Furthermore, the proposed new method is applicable to Young's modulus measurement in a thin layer formed by PVD (Physical Vapor Deposition), CVD (Chemical Vapor Deposition), Electrodeposition, Coating (Graphite, Metal Oxide), Paint (Lacquer), Cladding, Lamination, etc.

Besides the *Own-Weight Multi-layered Cantilever Method* studied here, the *Axial Compression Method* [1], [2], the *Cantilever Method* [3], the *Circular Ring Method* [4], [5], the *Own-Weight Cantilever Method* [6] for a flexible single-layered material and More the *Axial Compression Method* [7], the *Cantilever Method* [8], the *Circular Ring Method* [9], [10], for a flexible multi-layered material have already been developed and reported, based on the nonlinear large deformation theory. On the other hand, since it is really very difficult to measure Young's modulus of a thin layer mentioned above, various methods [11], [12], [13] have been studied on the basis of the linear

deformation theory (: small deformation theory) for metallic films and foils. In addition, the basic large deformation problems were dealt with in the past and may be consulted [14], [15].

2 THEORY

For small deformations, there are some testing methods, e.g. three- or four-point bending test for evaluating mechanical properties of various materials. These conventional tests are commonly used to obtain Young's modulus because of their simplicity. Although these methods are very simple, they also have several disadvantages (e.g., a stress concentration around a loading nose, a gripping problem of specimen). Since the conventional methods are based on the small deformation theory, these methods are inapplicable directly to large deformation problems. Therefore, as the deformations of specimen grow larger, a more exact analysis is required to obtain accurate results. From this point of view, a new testing method (*Own-Weight Cantilever Method*) is derived considering large deformation behaviors of a test specimen. The new method can be applied to various thin, long fiber materials (Glass fibers, Carbon fibers, Optical fibers, etc.) and thin sheet materials.

2.1 Basic equations [14,15]

Major premises for the analysis are as follows:

- (1) The scope of the large deformation theory is used within the elastic range.
- (2) The Euler-Bernoulli's assumption is applicable.
- (3) Poisson's effect is not considered and shear deformation is neglected.
- (4) The multi-layered material is considered to be inextensible.

A typical illustration of deflections is given in Fig.1 for a multi-layered cantilever (length L) subjected to the total own-weight $w (= \sum_{i=1}^n w_i)$ consisted of n layers where w_i is the distributed load per unit length of each layer in a multi-layered material with a supporting angle θ_0 . As an example, Figure 2 shows the cross-section of a two-layered material ($n=2$). The horizontal displacement is denoted by x , the vertical displacement by y , and θ is the deflection angle. Furthermore, the arc length is denoted by s , the radius of curvature by R and the bending moment by M . The relationships between $R, M, s, x,$

Figure 1: Large deflections of a multi-layered cantilever subjected to own-weight.

Figure 2: Illustration of cross-section of two-layered material (as an example).

y and θ are given by:

$$\frac{1}{R} = -\frac{d\theta}{ds} = \frac{M}{\sum_{i=1}^n (E_i I_i)}, \quad dx = ds \cdot \cos \theta, \quad dy = ds \cdot \sin \theta \quad (1)$$

where E_i, I_i are Young's modulus, the second moment of area at an arbitrary layer respectively and $E_i I_i$ is the flexural rigidity of each layer.

On the other hand, the horizontal displacement at an arbitrary point \bar{Q} between the point O and the point Q is denoted by \bar{y} , the arc length by \bar{s} , the infinitesimal arc length $d\bar{s}$ at an arbitrary point \bar{Q} , and putting V_0 as the vertical reaction at the origin O, M_0 as the bending moment at the origin O and Y as the integral of \bar{y} , the bending moment M applied at an arbitrary position Q (x, y) is

$$\begin{aligned} M &= V_0 \cdot y - M_0 - \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \int_0^y (y - \bar{y}) d\bar{s} = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i L \cdot y - M_0 - \sum_{i=1}^n w_i [y\bar{s} - Y]_0^s \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n w_i L \cdot y - M_0 - \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \{ys - Y(s) + Y(0)\} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where the function $Y(s)$ shows the first integral of \bar{y} .

The basic equation is derived from Eqs.(1) and (2) in the form of:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (E_i I_i) \frac{d^2 \theta}{ds^2} + \sum_{i=1}^n w_i (L - s) \sin \theta = 0 \quad (3)$$

Introducing the following non-dimensional variables and transforming the variables,

$$\xi = \frac{x}{L}, \quad \eta = \frac{y}{L}, \quad \zeta = \frac{s}{L}, \quad \gamma = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i L^3}{\sum_{i=1}^n (E_i I_i)}, \quad \beta = \frac{ML}{\sum_{i=1}^n (E_i I_i)} \quad (4)$$

and transforming the variables ($s \rightarrow \zeta$), equation (3) reduces to Eq.(5).

$$\frac{d^2 \theta}{d\zeta^2} + \gamma(1 - \zeta) \sin \theta = 0 \quad (5)$$

Assuming the following relationships in Eq.(5),

$$\psi = \theta - \frac{\theta_A + \theta_0}{2} \quad \left[-\frac{\theta_A - \theta_0}{2} \leq \psi \leq \frac{\theta_A - \theta_0}{2} \right] \quad (6)$$

finally, the nonlinear differential equation concerning the new variable ψ is obtained as follows.

$$\frac{d^2 \psi}{d\zeta^2} + \gamma(1 - \zeta) \left\{ \cos\left(\frac{\theta_A + \theta_0}{2}\right) \cdot \sin \psi + \sin\left(\frac{\theta_A + \theta_0}{2}\right) \cdot \cos \psi \right\} = 0 \quad (7)$$

where

$$\sin \psi = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} 2 \cdot \sin\left(\frac{n \cdot \pi}{2}\right) \cdot J_n\left(\frac{\theta_A - \theta_0}{2}\right) \cdot T_n\left(\frac{2\psi}{\theta_A - \theta_0}\right) \quad (8)$$

$$\cos \psi = J_0\left(\frac{\theta_A - \theta_O}{2}\right) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 2 \cdot \cos\left(\frac{n \cdot \pi}{2}\right) \cdot J_n\left(\frac{\theta_A - \theta_O}{2}\right) \cdot T_n\left(\frac{2\psi}{\theta_A - \theta_O}\right) \quad (9)$$

The functions $T_n(x)$, $J_n(x)$ appearing in Eqs.(8), (9) are Chebyshev polynimial and Bessel function respectively. Here, concise equations (10) [$n=1$ in Eq.(8)], (11) [$n=0$ in Eq.(9)] instead of Eqs.(10),(11) are adopted for the simplicity of numerical treatments.

$$\sin \psi \cong 4J_1\left(\frac{\theta_A - \theta_O}{2}\right) \cdot \frac{\psi}{\theta_A - \theta_O} \quad (10)$$

$$\cos \psi \cong J_0\left(\frac{\theta_A - \theta_O}{2}\right) \quad (11)$$

From Eqs.(7), (10), and (11),:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2\psi}{d\zeta^2} - \left\{ \frac{4J_1\left(\frac{\theta_A - \theta_O}{2}\right) \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\theta_A + \theta_O}{2}\right)}{\theta_A - \theta_O} \right\} \psi \cdot \gamma \cdot (1 - \zeta) \\ = -J_0\left(\frac{\theta_A - \theta_O}{2}\right) \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\theta_A + \theta_O}{2}\right) \cdot \gamma \cdot (1 - \zeta) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

and introducing the following relationships shown in Eqs.(13)-(16),:

$$\delta = \gamma \cdot (1 - \zeta) \quad [0 \leq \delta \leq \gamma] \quad (13)$$

$$q = - \frac{(\theta_A - \theta_O) \cdot J_0\left(\frac{\theta_A - \theta_O}{2}\right) \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\theta_A + \theta_O}{2}\right)}{4J_1\left(\frac{\theta_A - \theta_O}{2}\right) \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\theta_A + \theta_O}{2}\right)} \quad (14)$$

$$m^2 = - \frac{16J_1\left(\frac{\theta_A - \theta_O}{2}\right) \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\theta_A + \theta_O}{2}\right)}{9\gamma^2 \cdot (\theta_A - \theta_O)} \quad (15)$$

$$u = \psi - q \quad (16)$$

finally, Bessel's differential equation (19) is derived from Eq.(12):

$$\frac{d^2u}{d\delta^2} - \left(\frac{3}{2}m\right)^2 \delta u = 0 \quad (17)$$

Using the modified Bessel function $I_n(x)$, the solution of Eq.(19) is obtained as follows.

$$u = \delta^{1/2} \left\{ K_1 \cdot I_{1/3}(m \cdot \delta^{3/2}) + K_2 \cdot I_{-1/3}(m \cdot \delta^{3/2}) \right\} \quad (K_1, K_2 : \text{constant}) \quad (18)$$

Therefore, the variable ψ in Eq.(6) is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \psi &= \delta^{1/2} \left\{ K_1 \cdot I_{1/3} (m \cdot \delta^{3/2}) + K_2 \cdot I_{-1/3} (m \cdot \delta^{3/2}) \right\} + q \quad (19) \\ &= K_1 \frac{m^{1/3}}{2^{1/3} \cdot \Gamma(4/3)} \left\{ \delta + \frac{m^2 \cdot \delta^4}{2 \cdot (8/3)} + \frac{m^4 \cdot \delta^7}{2 \cdot 4 \cdot (8/3) \cdot (14/3)} + \dots \right\} \\ &\quad + K_2 \frac{m^{-1/3}}{2^{-1/3} \cdot \Gamma(2/3)} \left\{ 1 + \frac{m^2 \cdot \delta^3}{2 \cdot (4/3)} + \frac{m^4 \cdot \delta^6}{2 \cdot 4 \cdot (8/3) \cdot (10/3)} + \dots \right\} + q \end{aligned}$$

where the function $\Gamma(x)$ appearing in Eq.(19) is the Gamma function.

Considering the boundary conditions $d\psi/d\delta|_{\delta=0}=0$ (i.e., $d\theta/ds|_{\zeta=1}=0$) and $\psi|_{\delta=0}=(\theta_A-\theta_0)/2$ (i.e., $\theta|_{\zeta=1}=\theta_A$: the deflection angle at the free end A), the constant K_1, K_2 in Eq.(18) (or (19)) are shown as

$$K_1 = 0 \quad (20)$$

$$K_2 = \left\{ \frac{m^{1/3} \cdot \Gamma(2/3)}{2^{1/3}} \right\} \left(\frac{\theta_A - \theta_0}{2} - q \right) \quad (21)$$

In consequence, the non-dimensional horizontal displacement ξ and the non-dimensional vertical displacement η at an arbitrary position Q (x, y) can be calculated from Eqs.(1), (19)-(21).

Finally, the non-dimensional maximum horizontal displacement $\xi_A (= \xi_{max}=x_A/L)$ (x_A : horizontal displacement at the free end A) and the non-dimensional maximum vertical displacement $\eta_A (= \eta_{max}=y_A/L)$ (y_A : vertical displacement at the free end A) are obtained as follows.

$$\xi_A = \int_0^{\zeta_A} \cos \theta d\zeta \quad (22)$$

$$= \int_0^{\zeta_A} \cos \left[\frac{\left(\frac{\theta_A - \theta_0}{2} - q \right) \left\{ 1 + \frac{m^2 \cdot \delta^3}{2 \cdot (4/3)} + \frac{m^4 \cdot \delta^6}{2 \cdot 4 \cdot (8/3) \cdot (10/3)} + \dots \right\}}{+ q + \frac{\theta_A + \theta_0}{2}} \right] d\zeta$$

$$\eta_A = \int_0^{\zeta_A} \sin \theta d\zeta \quad (23)$$

$$= \int_0^{\zeta_A} \sin \left[\frac{\left(\frac{\theta_A - \theta_0}{2} - q \right) \left\{ 1 + \frac{m^2 \cdot \delta^3}{2 \cdot (4/3)} + \frac{m^4 \cdot \delta^6}{2 \cdot 4 \cdot (8/3) \cdot (10/3)} + \dots \right\}}{+ q + \frac{\theta_A + \theta_0}{2}} \right] d\zeta$$

In view of the constant K_1, K_2 and the boundary condition $\psi|_{\delta=\gamma} = -(\theta_A-\theta_0)/2$ (i.e., $\theta|_{\zeta=0}=\theta_0$: the deflection angle at the fixed end O), the following equation (24) is derived. Consequently, the deflection angle θ_A at the free end A can be obtained.

$$\frac{\theta_A - \theta_0}{2} = - \left(\frac{\theta_A - \theta_0}{2} - q \right) \left\{ 1 + \frac{m^2 \cdot \gamma^3}{2 \cdot (4/3)} + \frac{m^4 \cdot \gamma^6}{2 \cdot 4 \cdot (8/3) \cdot (10/3)} + \dots \right\} + q \quad (24)$$

Equations (22)-(24) are the fundamental formulae based on the nonlinear large deformation theory to obtain Young's modulus of each layer in a flexible multi-layered material using the own-weight cantilever with an arbitrary supporting angle θ_0 . From the viewpoint of the experiment, however, it is

very simple and convenient to support a vertical cantilever as a support technique of beams. Therefore, considering the availability of the new cantilever method, Young's modulus measurement at the supporting angle of $\theta_0=0$ (that is, vertical condition) is described in the following section as a special case of "Own-Weight Multi-layered Cantilever Method".

As known from Eqs.(22)-(24), the formulae for measuring Young's modulus, based on the nonlinear large deformation theory are complicated in general. The following formula based on Eq.(6) is useful in calculating each Young's modulus E_i .

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (E_i I_i) - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i L^3}{\gamma} = 0 \quad (25)$$

In order to calculate each Young's modulus E_i using Eq.(25), it is necessary to determine the neutral axis of multi-layered plates.

The second moment of area I_i of each cross section (thickness h_i , width b : common to all) with respect to the neutral axis is shown as

$$I_i = \frac{bh_i^3}{12} + bh_i \left(\bar{x} - \frac{h_i}{2} - \sum_{k=1}^n h_{k-1} \right)^2 \quad (h_0 = 0, i \leq n) \quad (26)$$

The distance \bar{x} to the neutral axis (see Fig.2) is obtained as follows.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n E_i (S_i)_z}{\sum_{i=1}^n (E_i A_i)} \quad (27)$$

Furthermore, the first moment of area $(S_i)_z$ of each cross section (A_i : the cross-sectional area) with respect to z axis is expressed as

$$(S_i)_z = \frac{bh_i^2}{2} + bh_i \left(\sum_{k=1}^n h_{k-1} \right) \quad (28)$$

In case of multi-layered rods, it is unnecessary to determine the neutral axis because the cross section is symmetrical at any time with respect to the neutral axis. The second moment of area I_i of each cross section for multi-layered wires (or rods) (outer diameter d_i) with respect to the neutral axis is shown as

$$I_i = \frac{\pi(d_i^4 - d_{i-1}^4)}{64} \quad (d_0 = 0) \quad (29)$$

In order to calculate each Young's modulus E_i from Eq. (27), One quantity γ (: the non-dimensional load) is required and so the usage of the chart is recommended in this paper by the author for the sake of simplicity.

2.2 Measuring techniques (vertical cantilever at the supporting angle of $\theta_0=0$)

Two representative methods to know the value of γ are introduced here. The original data is a horizontal displacement x_A or a vertical displacement y_A . Two charts (Nomographs) of $\gamma-x_A/L$ ($:\xi_A$) relation (see Fig.3) and $\gamma-y_A/L$ ($:\eta_A$) relation (see Fig.4) are presented respectively.

These charts were computed previously by using Eqs.(22)-(24). The calculation is repeated until the assumed angle θ_A at the free end coincides with the calculated angle θ_A based on Eq.(24). When the two values agree with each other, the deformed shape (in other words, $\gamma-x_A/L(:\xi_A)$ relation, $\gamma-y_A/L(:\eta_A)$ relation) is determined ultimately.

In Figs.3 and 4, various sketches represent deformed beams (symbol \bullet) on the specific conditions x_A, y_A .

Using the chart (: Nomograph) of $\gamma-x_A/L(:\xi_A)$ relation (x_A : the horizontal displacement) [Method 1] or $\gamma-y_A/L(:\eta_A)$ relation (y_A : the vertical displacement) [Method 2], each Young's modulus in a multi-layered material can be easily obtained.

As a point to note, for example, a two-step procedure (Refer to Step 1 and Step 2 in Subsection 2.2.1 and 2.2.2) should be done in a measuring experiment, when Young's modulus of each layer in a two-layered material is all unknown (Note that a multi-layered material with number of layers n requires a n - step procedure). In other words, it is possible to reduce a frequency of step in proportion to the number, if the number of layers with known Young's modulus is proven.

2.2.1 Method 1: Measurement of x_A only

As an example, the usage of this method is shown below in a two-layered material. Each Young's modulus E_i is obtained for a SUS layer (first layer) with length: $L_1=350.0$ [mm], width: $b_1=27.0$ [mm], thickness: $h_1=0.100$ [mm], distributed load per unit length: $w_1=210.88 \times 10^{-3}$ [N/m] and a PVC layer (second layer) with length: $L_2(=L_1)=350.0$ [mm], width: $b_2(=b_1)=27.0$ [mm], thickness: $h_2=0.200$ [mm], distributed load per unit length: $w_2=73.55 \times 10^{-3}$ [N/m].

A chart (Nomograph) is given in Fig.3, illustrating the relationship of γ and x_A/L (: ξ_A) [shown in Eq.(22)]. Using this chart, each Young's modulus E_i in a multi-layered material can be calculated from the relational expression given in Eq.(25).

[Step 1]:1st step procedure(As a two-layered specimen)

Under the condition of $L(=L_1=L_2)=350.0$ [mm], $x_A=121.3$ [mm] (i.e., $\xi_A=x_A/L=0.3466$) is m for a double layer and then the value of γ is taken from Fig.3 ($\gamma=11.1711$). Therefore, using the combined flexural rigidity (I_1, I_2 : unknown) is derived as follows.

Figure 3: Non-dimensional chart for the finding the parameter γ when the horizontal displacement x_A is given.

Figure 4: Non-dimensional chart for the finding the parameter γ when the vertical displacement y_A is given.

$$E_1 I_1 + E_2 I_2 = \frac{(w_1 + w_2)L^3}{\gamma} = \frac{(210.88 + 73.55) \times 10^{-3} \times 0.35^3}{11.1711} = 1.0917 \times 10^{-3} \quad (30)$$

[Step 2]:2nd step procedure(As a single-layered specimen)

Similarly, x_A is measured for a single layer after removing a second layer (PVC). In the condition of $L=290.0$ [mm] for a SUS single layer, $x_A=60.3$ [mm] (i.e., $\xi_A=x_A/L=0.2079$) is measured and γ is taken newly from Fig.3 ($\gamma=12.4880$). Therefore, the flexural rigidity ($I_1=2.25 \times 10^{-15}$ [m⁴]: SUS, I_2 : unknown) can be rewritten as follows from Eq.(25).

$$E_1 = \frac{w_1 L^3}{\gamma I_1} = \frac{210.88 \times 10^{-3} \times 0.29^3}{12.488 \times 2.25 \times 10^{-15}} \cong 183.05 \times 10^9 \text{ [N/m}^2\text{]} = 183.05 \text{ [GPa]} \quad (31)$$

Using Eqs.(26), (27) and applying the false position method to the simultaneous equations (30), (31), Young's modulus E_1 , E_2 of each layer is calculated to be $E_1=183.05$ [GPa] for a SUS layer and $E_2=3.67$ [GPa] for a PVC layer.

2.2.2 Method 2: Measurement of y_A only

A similar chart (Nomograph) is given in Fig.4, illustrating the relationship of γ and y_A/L (η_A) [shown in Eq. (23)]. Using this chart, each Young's modulus E_i in a multi-layered material can be calculated from Eq.(25). As an example, Young's modulus E_i of each layer in a two-layered material is obtained for a SUS thin layer (first layer) + a PVC thin layer (second layer) mentioned above (see Subsection 2.2.1).

[Step 1]:1st step procedure(As a two-layered specimen)

Under the condition of $L (=L_1=L_2)=350.0$ [mm], $y_A=282.3$ [mm] (i.e., $\eta_A=y_A/L=0.8066$) is measured for a double layer and then the value of γ is taken from Fig.4 ($\gamma=10.7158$). Therefore, from Eq.(25) the combined flexural rigidity (I_1, I_2 : unknown) can be written as follows.

$$E_1 I_1 + E_2 I_2 = \frac{(w_1 + w_2)L^3}{\gamma} = \frac{(210.88 + 73.55) \times 10^{-3} \times 0.35^3}{10.7158} = 1.1381 \times 10^{-3} \quad (32)$$

[Step 2]:2nd step procedure(As a single-layered specimen)

Similarly, y_A is measured for a single layer after removing a second layer (PVC). In the condition of $L=290.0$ [mm] for a SUS single layer, $y_A=228.6$ [mm] (i.e., $\eta_A=y_A/L=0.7883$) is measured and then γ is taken newly from Fig.4 ($\gamma=10.3278$). Therefore, the flexural rigidity ($I_1=2.25 \times 10^{-15}$ [m⁴]: SUS) can be rewritten as follows from Eq.(25).

$$E_1 = \frac{w_1 L^3}{\gamma I_1} = \frac{210.88 \times 10^{-3} \times 0.29^3}{10.3278 \times 2.25 \times 10^{-15}} \cong 221.33 \times 10^9 \text{ [N/m}^2\text{]} = 221.33 \text{ [GPa]} \quad (33)$$

From Eqs.(26), (27) and the simultaneous equations (32) and (33), Young's modulus E_1 , E_2 of each layer is calculated as $E_1=221.33$ [GPa] for a SUS layer and $E_2=3.06$ [GPa] for a PVC layer.

3 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

In order to assess the applicability of the Own-Weight Cantilever method, several experiments were carried out using a two-layered material [SUS layer: a stainless steel (length: $L_1=320.0$ [mm], width: $b_1=27.0$ [mm], thickness: $h_1=0.100$ [mm], distributed load per unit length: $w_1=210.88 \times 10^{-3}$ [N/m]) + PVC (Polyvinyl chloride) layer: a high-polymer material (length: $L_2 (=L_1) =320.0$ [mm], width: $b_2(=b_1) =27.0$ [mm], thickness: $h_2=0.200$ [mm], distributed load per unit length: $w_2=73.55 \times 10^{-3}$ [N/m])]. An experimental set-up is shown in Fig.5. Since Young's modulus of each layer in the two-

Figure 5: Experimental set-up (a multi-layered specimen).

layered material is unknown, the measuring experiments were carried out by adopting the two-step procedures. In every step of the procedures, a horizontal displacement x_A and a vertical displacement y_A at the free end are measured by using a grid paper with 1[mm] spacing. Here, the influence of the length upon Young's modulus was examined for several lengths of a cantilever.

Young's moduli of SUS and PVC obtained by applying Method 1 and Method 2 are shown in Figs. 6 and 7, respectively. Here, the influence of a length (L) upon Young's modulus (E) was examined. The figures were described under a two-layered condition (Note that similar figures were describable under a single-layered condition).

In a SUS layer (see Fig.6), the measured values of Method 1 and 2 remain nearly constant for various lengths L in the range of 170.0–440.0 [mm] and the standard deviation (S.D.) is small although every method has a little scattered values. That means Young's modulus shows a stable value considerably. As a whole, the mean Young's moduli (shown as Av.: Average) determined by the two methods are reasonably in good agreement with each other in error of 3.4% or so. As a reference, Young's modulus of SUS measured by using conventional three-point bending test based on the small deformation theory is $E_0=205.8$ [GPa].

On the other hand, Trends similar to that of Fig.6 is observed for Young's moduli of a PVC layer (see Fig.7). The mean values obtained by the two methods agree well in error of 9.3% or so. Therefore, there is little reason to choose between Method 1 and Method 2 to measure Young's modulus although Method 1 or 2 has a little scatter in the values. In this manner, Young's modulus can be obtained by applying an easy method (*Own-Weight Cantilever Method*) without a large scale testing machine.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The Own-Weight Cantilever Method is developed as a new and simpler material testing method for measuring Young's modulus of each layer in a thin flexible multi-layered material.

The principal conclusions are drawn as follows from the results of theoretical and experimental analyses.

Method 1(Data: x_A)

Method 1(Data: x_A)

Method 2(Data: y_A)

Method 2(Data: y_A)

Figure 6: Comparison of Young's moduli between the two measuring methods for a thin stainless material(SUS: E_1). [E_2 of PVC is known previously.]

Figure 7: Comparison of Young's moduli between the two measuring methods for a high-polymer material(PVC: E_2). [E_1 of SUS is known previously.]

- (1) The new method is based on the nonlinear large deformation theory.
- (2) Two representative charts (Nomographs) are drawn on the basis of the proposed theory for the sake of simplicity.
- (3) Based on the new idea, a set of testing devices was designed.
- (4) A thin two-layered material (a stainless steel material, SUS + a high-polymer material, PVC) was tested.
- (5) Experimental results clarify that the new method is suitable for measuring Young's modulus of each layer in a thin flexible multi-layered material.
- (6) Based on the assessments, the proposed method is applied to thin multi-layered sheets and thin multi-layered fiber materials (e.g., steel belts, glass fibers, carbon fibers, optical fibers, etc.).
- (7) Furthermore, the proposed method is applicable widely to Young's modulus measurement in a thin layer formed, for example, by PVD (Physical Vapor Deposition), CVD (Chemical Vapor Deposition), Electrodeposition, Coating (Graphite, Metal Oxide), Paint (Lacquer), etc.

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